

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET - CHILD

Version 1.0 Date 18 January 2021

Study Title: *Streptococcus pyogenes* carriage acquisition, persistence and transmission dynamics within households in The Gambia: a longitudinal cohort study - SpyCATS

SCC/Protocol No:	24005
------------------	-------

Sponsor: MRC Unit The Gambia at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

Funder: The Wellcome Trust

What is informed consent?

You are invited to let your child take part in a research study. Participating in a research study is not the same as getting regular medical care. The purpose of a research study is to gather information that may be useful in the future for the whole population. The purpose of this research study is to understand how a germ called Strep A is transmitted amongst adults and children living in the same household. It is your decision to let your child take part and they can stop at any time without giving any reason.

Before you decide to allow your child to join the study you need to understand why the study is being done and what will happen in it. Please take time to read the following information or get the information explained to you in your language. Listen carefully and feel free to ask if there is anything that you do not understand. As the study will involve your child but also your household and family, it is very important that you also discuss it amongst family members so that everyone is OK to take part too. If you decide to join the study, you and every adult in the household who is happy to contribute need to sign or thumbprint a consent form saying you understand and agree to be in the study. We will also ask your children if they are happy to take part if they are between 12 and 18 and get their agreement (assent), and you can give consent for your children in the household who are younger than 12. You will receive a copy of the form.

Why is this study being done?

Group A streptococcus, or "Strep A" is a germ that is very common all over the world, as well as in The Gambia. It usually causes infections of the throat and skin but can cause more serious illness and death. It can also lead to a type of heart disease, which is common in The Gambia.

Strep A can also live on people's skin and in their throats without making them sick, and we believe that this is how the germ passes between people. In this study we are trying to find out how common it is to carry Strep A on the skin or in the throat without being sick, how it spreads around households, and whether carrying Strep A is more likely to make you or your family sick in the future. If we can find these things out, we can design better ways to treat and prevent Strep A infections in The Gambia. We will tell the results of this study to your community.

Version	1.0	Date	18 January 2021
---------	-----	------	-----------------

SCC/Protocol No:

24005

What does this study involve?

The study will include 60 households from Sukuta, and if you agree for your child to take part in the study, we will visit you regularly at your home for a year. We will also ask all of the other people who live in your household to be in the study. We will normally visit the household every month, but in some cases more or less frequently depending if your child is selected for an additional part of the study.

At each visit, we will ask you some questions about your child, their health, and their usual daily activities. We will take their vital signs, and examine them, including their skin and throat. And we will take a swab from their throat, normal skin and any skin infections that we find, take a sample of their saliva, and some spots of dried blood. At some visits we will also ask to take a blood sample (if they are aged 2 years or more) or ask you to come with them to an appointment at Sukuta Health Centre to give a blood sample.

Each time we visit your household, we will also ask you or another member of your household some questions about the household such as sleeping arrangements and water access. We will also take some samples from the compound including swabs and leaving a dish indoors for 1 hour to collect germs from the air.

If we find out that your child is sick for any reason, they will receive the care routinely available in The Gambia. They may be provided with treatment at your compound, be asked to attend an MRC clinic or be referred to a health facility that can manage the condition better.

If the research study needs to be stopped for any reason, we will tell you and they will have normal medical care if they need it.

What will happen to the samples taken in this study?

The samples that we take at each visit will be taken to the MRC laboratories in Fajara. The swabs taken from your child's throat and skin, and the samples from the compound will be used to look for different germs including Strep A. The saliva sample, dried blood spots and blood samples will be used to test how the body's immune system reacts to Strep A. The samples may be sent to international laboratories.

With your permission, we will store all materials left over for any new research questions about Strep A that might come up in the future, and we ask you to tick the box on the consent form to say you are happy with having your samples stored for future use, which may include genetic testing. Any new research would have to be approved by the Gambia Government/MRC Joint Ethics Committee. If you do not wish to consent for future use of your child's samples, we can still have you participate but we would not store the samples.

What harm or discomfort can you expect in the study?

Your child may find that taking the swabs is uncomfortable, but it will be quick. The mouth swab for saliva does not hurt at all. The dried blood spots and blood samples can cause mild discomfort and might leave a small bruise, but the methods we are using are very safe, and the field team are well trained to take the samples as quickly and painlessly as possible.

Version	1.0	Date	18 January 2021
---------	-----	------	-----------------

What benefits can you expect in the study?

The benefit to your child, you and your household members is that you will have regular visits from our nursing team who will examine your child and identify any Strep A infections, or other medical problems earlier than normal. The study team will also provide treatment for any possible Strep A infections, and some other common medical problems to your child for free at the household visits.

Your child would also have access to our doctors and nurses in case you have another medical problem, and we can advise you and your family what to do. If we think they need to go into hospital, we will refer them to the governmental health facilities for routine care for such conditions. In some cases, we might take them to MRC hospital in Fajara.

Will you be compensated for participating in the study?

You will not get paid by the study for participation, but if your child has to attend the clinic for a study-related reason with, MRC will provide transport or give you back the money for your transport.

What happens if you refuse to participate in the study or change your mind later?

You are free to let your child join the study or not and you are free to stop taking part in the study any time without giving a reason. You and your child will still get the normal medical care. If you do not want your child to continue in the study, we will use only the samples and information already collected from your child. If any new information becomes available during the study that may affect your child's participation, you will be informed as soon as possible.

How will personal records remain confidential and who will have access to it?

All information that is collected about your child will be kept strictly confidential. Their personal information will only be available to the study team members and might be seen by some rightful persons from the Ethics Committee, Government authorities and sponsor. This could include organisations outside The Gambia. Anybody outside the study team who might see such information would only do so to ensure the study was being conducted properly.

Who should you contact if you have questions?

If you have any questions or are worried you can call [REDACTED] and you can always call the personal numbers of the MRC workers given to you. Please feel free to ask any question you might have about the study.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been checked by scientists at the Medical Research Council and by the Gambia Government/MRC Joint Ethics Committee. The Ethics Committee protects your rights and wellbeing and has given permission for it to take place.

SCC/Protocol No: 24005

CONSENT / ASSENT FORM

Household Identification Number: |__|__|__| Individual Identification Number: |__|__|__|

Participant's Name: _____

_____ **OR** _____
 (Printed name of parent) (Printed name of guardian)

- I have read the written information **OR**
- I have had the information explained to me by study personnel in a language that I understand, and I:

- confirm that my choice to let my child participate is entirely voluntarily,
- confirm that I have had the opportunity to ask questions about this study and I am happy with the answers that have been provided,
- understand that I allow access to the information about my child by the persons described in the information sheet,
- had enough time to think about whether I want my child to take part in this study,
- agree to allow my child to take part in this study.

Cross (X) as appropriate

I agree for my child's samples to be shipped outside of The Gambia Yes No

I agree to storage and future research on my child's samples/our household samples including genetic testing Yes No

Participant's signature/thumbprint* for **assent** (child aged 12-17 years)

_____ Date Time

Participant's parent/guardian signature/thumbprint*

_____ Date Time

Printed name of witness* _____

Printed Name of Person obtaining consent _____

I attest that I have explained the study information accurately in _____ and was understood to the best of my knowledge by, the participant/parent/guardian. He/she has freely given consent to participate *in the presence of the above named witness (where applicable).

Signature of Person obtaining consent _____

_____ Date (dd/mmm/yyyy) Time (24hr)

* Only required if the participant is unable to read or write.